

Transformational Leadership Moderates the Relationship Between Servant Leadership and Disengagement

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Abstract

Organizational leadership is the dominant function of management. It contributes to reducing burnout and stress and plays a significant role in promoting mental health and relaxation. The study intended to examine the effect of servant leadership on burnout dimensions, especially disengagement among the health sector employees in the district of Swabi Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. Furthermore, this study tested the moderating effect of transformational leadership in a relationship with servant leadership on disengagement. The population of this study was employees of the health sector in the Swabi district and the data were collected through questionnaires from 229 respondents. The study found that servant leadership positively affects employee disengagement, while transformational leadership moderates the relationship between servant leadership and disengagement. The findings provide significant implications for policymakers, especially for the health sector and generally for every sector underpinning for low disengagement among employees in organizations. Furthermore, this study flourishes the body of knowledge about leadership on the attribute of employees in developing countries. Future research on the effect of servant leadership with an autocratic leadership style on employee burnout in other sectors like the education and industrial sectors may be investigated.

Keywords: Disengagement, Servant Leadership, Transformational Leadership, Health Sector, Moderation

1. Introduction

Leadership is one of the most critical topics; everything in an organization depends on it. A leader often provides and encourages a productive structure for the organization, using planning, efficiency, and productivity, and tends to be directive, goal-oriented, functional, and effective motivators. According to Robbins (2005), it involves influencing individuals toward achieving organizational goals. Many leadership eras have emerged fast and consistently in the present age (King, 1990; Zhou, Liu, & Xin, 2022). Various leadership styles have also been studied, including autocratic, democratic, and coaching (Tannenbaum and Schmidt, 2017). Focusing on employees' "preferred self" (cognitive, emotional, physical engagement) leads to more productive organizations (Kahn, 1990). Several issues related to work behavior have been studied by recent research, primarily burnout, knowledge sharing, motivation, and innovation (Khan., Sufyan, Hussain, & Gul, 2022; Najam, Ishaque, Shoukat, Hayat Awan, & Ansari, 2018).

Employees in all sectors experience burnout. Employees with this characteristic have a negative attitude. A lack of high-level management, including organization leaders, contributes to low morale and high burnout in the health sector (Farrington & Lillah, 2018; Faisal Khan, Ali, Bashir, & Naz, 2021). As a result, the current study provides new insights into the two leadership styles, Servant Leadership and Transformational Leadership, concerning burnout in the healthcare industry, especially emotional exhaustion and disengagement.

In the current hectic organizational culture, transformational leadership is the most common research topic (Divya & Suganthi, 2018). Gong believes it is firmly connected to organizational and personnel development. Originally, transformational leadership was coined by Tavanti (1978). Additionally, the author concluded that transformational leadership alters the values and perceptions of employees and the organization. According to Engelen, Gupta, Strenger and Brettell (2015), transformational leadership motivates, inspires, and stimulates employees to achieve organizational objectives.

According to House (2011), some people are motivated to help others for religious reasons, while others are passionate about helping others. This passion for serving others is a hallmark of Motivation for Health Care Professionals (Trastek, Hamilton, & Niles, 2014). Similarly, servant Leadership focuses on serving others and is more suitable in the health sector (Farrington & Lillah, 2018; Jafai, Moghadam, & Hosseini, 2016). Serving nature is inherently a servant leadership characteristic, the type of leadership needed among employees (Schwartz, 2002). So, the second variable of interest in the study is Servant Leadership, introduced by Leaf (1970). Stone, Russell, and Patterson (2004), also suggest that servant leaders pay attention to their employees' choices, needs, and satisfaction. A servant leader sets goals, develops employees, and strives to improve the overall performance of an organization. According to Madana Kumar (2013), servant Leadership is different from other leadership styles; Servant Leadership is focused on the welfare of the employees. It shows that servant leadership possesses a high quality of humanity. Moreover, those organizations with a good environment wish to convert to excellence, which is possible only through the humble nature of the leader.

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Burnout is prolonged stress observed within people who “do work” (Maslach & Jackson, 1986). According to the authors' main three dimensions, that is emotional exhaustion (a more chronic form of mental and physical stress), Depersonalization or cynicism (development of negative thoughts toward work) and personal accomplishment (lack of achieving the objective in the workplace shows poor performance). According to the researcher, burnout has become increasingly common over the past few decades, leading to emotional exhaustion and disengagement (Bakker., Demerouti., & Schaufeli., 2002; Haider & Ali, 2015; Faisal Khan, Khan, Malik, & Qureshi, 2017; Faisal Khan, Khan, Naz, & Rasli, 2016; Kassem et al., 2019). An extreme form of fatigue, emotional exhaustion is characterized by intense and prolonged affective, cognitive, and physical stress (Roussel et al., 2021; F Khan. et al., 2014; Lee & Ashforth, 1996). Freudenberg (1974) defined disengagement as the inability to engage with one's work. A person involved in a conflict and not interested in completing their work (Faisal Khan, Yusoff, & Khan, 2014).

In the last decade, several researchers have studied leadership, including Liden (2008), Van Dierendonck (2011) and Neubert (2008). The health sector still receives less attention than other sectors, and few people know how to lead medical leaders (Chapman, Johnson, & Kilner, 2014). Attachment of the employees towards the organization highly depends on the behavior of leaders. Moreover, leadership reduces stress and burnout (Babakus, Yavas, & Ashill, 2010; Faisal Khan, Nisar, & Malik, 2020; Nasir et al., 2021). Employee health programs and employee assistance programs are effective in reducing burnout.

Furthermore, Transformational leadership is one of the dominant types of leadership in Pakistan's health sector and employees' emotional feelings positively link to transformational (Rasool, Arfeen, Mothi, & Aslam, 2015; Sajid & Ali, 2018; Senturk & Ali, 2021). Moreover, significant relationships between transformational and Servant leadership (Divya & Suganthi, 2018). Implementing Servant Leadership within an organization reduces the frustration and exhaustion of employees (Sheikh, Ishaq, & Inam, 2019). Similarly, according to the researchers study Stone, Russell and Patterson (2004), both the leadership show care and concern for employees. However, Servant leadership is concerned with followers and transformational leadership greatly interests organizational objectives. Servant Leadership motivates the employees through their well-being and care, while transformational leadership motivates employees through organizational objectives.

Leaders who serve others are servant leaders who encourage an environment that reduces burnout and increases self-esteem, which leads to employees' Commitment (Badshah Hussain, Waseem, Farooq, & Khan, 2021; Sheikh et al., 2019). Feelings are brought to employees. Moreover, the study concluded that Servant Leadership's effect on the organization is positive. James and Coulter (2010) highlight the importance of transformative leadership in motivating and inspiring employees to achieve their goals. Moreover, In Divya and Suganthi's (2018) study, transformational employees' leadership styles are influenced by their leadership styles. There must be a combination of other forms of leadership to create transformational leadership (Zhu, Sosik, Riggio, & Yang, 2012). In contrast, transformational leadership has also been studied in studies on management (Faisal Khan, S. Nisar, et al., 2020).

From the above discussion, the researchers observed that this study would examine transformational and servant leadership in the district of Swabi Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan, and their effects on employee disengagement. Additionally, this study will use various supporting theories to develop a conceptual framework for the variables. Further, the researcher formulated the following research Objectives.

- To investigate the effect of Servant Leadership on disengagement among employees of the health sector in Swabi district, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.
- To determine the moderation effect of Transformational Leadership on the relationship between Servant Leadership and disengagement among the health sector employees in district Swabi Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

1.1. Significance of the Study

The current study is significant implications for researchers, employees, organizations, and policymakers. The purpose of the study is to provide a model theory on the moderation effect of transformational leadership concerning Servant Leadership and Disengagement in the health sector in the district of Swabi Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Additionally, the present study will provide the researcher with information about the study's variables and their direct and indirect relationships. It will help the body of knowledge in the form of literature, especially in the health sector and generally in any industry.

Furthermore, this study is to identify the literature regarding Servant and Transformational Leadership and Disengagement. There will be an awareness-raising session about leadership in the health sector as a result of this session. Knowledge about the characteristics of a good leader in the health sector will be helpful for the training of leaders. Furthermore, this study will provide information about the two leadership used within the organization. It will offer more scope for organizational leadership and recognition of burnout, especially Disengagement. Leaders of the organization will be aware of how to retain satisfied employees and reduce Disengagement (Sipe and Frick, 2009). Previous studies have shown that employees are an organization's most valuable asset; therefore, this research will benefit employees. Empirical results will nurture policymakers' decision-making capabilities.

Additionally, the researcher hopes to identify management and leadership initiatives in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. The current study will also be beneficial in producing committed employees by using different leadership styles. Its conclusion will also serve as a guide for policymakers, organizational leaders, and others interested in the impact of leadership in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa's health sector.

2. Concept of Variables

The researcher explained the concept of the variables with the help of previous studies' concerns with the current study variables. Research has been conducted on Different leadership styles, servant and transformational leadership, as well as burnout's role in disengagement. Based on previous knowledge, the researchers will demonstrate the current study.

2.1. Concept of Transformational Leadership

According to Bushra, Ahmad and Naveed (2011), transformational leadership is a form of leadership in which leaders and followers have high morals and motivation. It is an approach to consider the modern approach in this era. In addition, transformational leadership's vision, strength, and personality can inspire followers to achieve the organization's goals by changing motivation, perception, and expectations. Transformational leadership is described as a unique method of changing and transforming employees through motivation.

Transformational leaders focus more on motivating employees toward organizational objectives. In addition to gaining trust, admiration and respect from their followers, transformational leaders inspire employees to work more productively with motivation. Employees become more aware of the importance of achieving objectives and goals through their training, resulting in a greater sense of ownership for positive impacts. A transformational leader impacts employee behavior (Al-Swidi., Nawawi., & Al-Hosam., 2012). Transformational leadership allows employees to think creatively, analyze the problem in a new way, and find a solution to the problem with new technologies. In addition to increasing the capabilities and skills of the employee, transformational leadership also aligns employee goals with organizational objectives (Rasool et al., 2015). There are four primary positive effects of consideration and intellectual stimulation.

By demonstrating ethical and moral factors in organizational decision-making, charisma or idealized influence can inspire employees and create respect among followers. Employees are strongly impressed by the characteristics of a leader. Assume that a leader is an ideal person, resulting in a positive influence on the employees. An inspirational leader inspires the organizational culture positively through vision, decision-making, attitude, and actions. A leader's primary focus in grooming employees is to enhance employee motivation, help them incorporate leadership qualities, and enable them to take responsibility for team building in productive ways. The impact of transformational leadership on organizational innovation is positive.

Individualized consideration suggests transformational leadership focuses on employees individually, understands values, beliefs, and culture, and provides feedback. It develops self-efficacy and positive motivation in employees. It positively impacts employees' emotional feelings. Emotional feeling is positively correlated with transformational leadership. Transformational leadership could stimulate employees to go beyond expected results and create a positive work environment.

As defined by Smith (2004), intellectual stimulation is the quality of transformational leadership that involves encouraging creativity and innovation, accepting more processes, providing an environment in which employees can sharpen their skills, and taking risks to benefit the organization in the long run.

Transformational leadership has a more significant positive impact on individuals and organizations. Supervisors who possess transformational leadership qualities create more empowered and productive employees. However, leaders who use transformational leadership positively influence organizational culture, competitive advantages, and learning.

2.2. Concept of Servant Leadership

Servant Leadership is created by the 'servant' and the 'leader.' Although these two words are often opposite, Servant Leadership includes many positive qualities, including ethical and spiritual (Hoch, Bommer, Dulebohn, & Wu, 2018). In 1970, Leaf introduced servant leadership. A servant leader serves others first, says the author. According to Peterson, Galvin, and Lange (2012), servant leadership is one of the most critical elements of an organization's success. Serving others and oneself heals people who suffer from emotional hurts and lose their spirits at work when servant leadership is combined. Still, Servant Leadership provides an opportunity to help and encourage them (Greenleaf, 2008). The leader understands the employee's needs and provides support and assistance because the leader shares behavioral norms and expectations (Liden et al., 2008).

According to Stone et al., (2004), servant leadership is necessary for long-term organizational growth. The researcher further describes the servant leader as the stage of moral development and caring for others. Sun states that serving as a servant is part of Servant Leadership from an extended perspective. It focuses on the employees' well-being, growth, and development. It is primarily concerned with the employees' moral needs and the ability to satisfy them.

Servant leadership refers to a leader's efforts to increase employee satisfaction and create favorable work conditions (Divya & Suganthi, 2018). By serving employees, supervisors positively influence the behavior of their subordinates (Leaf, 1970).

According to Searle and Barbuto (2011), servant leadership increases confidence. A servant leader understands fundamental human values and needs the power to influence subordinates with various human values, support for human consideration, and various human values. To motivate their employees, they use their power and influence. In Spears' (1998) definition, servant leadership involves ten dimensions: empathy, persuasion, listening, healing, foresight, awareness, community building, stewardship, growth commitment to people, and conceptualization. As described by Barbuto and Wheeler (2002), these characteristics are coupled with another dimension, 'Calling,' that refers to serving others. Servant leadership comprises five sub-dimensions: valuing people, sharing leadership, displaying authenticity, creating community, and providing leadership. Also, different researchers have developed servant leadership models (Stone et al., 2004). There are 11 characteristics of servant leadership (Barbuto and Wheeler, 2002).

Servants are motivated by serving behaviors, which is fundamental to servant leadership (Leaf, 1970) and the concept of calling provides life meaning to others. The concept of leadership without self-interest is similar to the concept of calling (Conger, 1993) argues that altruism and calls are similar. For leaders, empathy is the key to listening; it is the main component of understanding employees' emotions and needs (Wolff and Kat, 2002). It is crucial for leaders for good management of teams; it enhances loyalty toward leaders (Cosolido, 2002). Leaders should be empathic (Shuster, 1994). In the same way, these studies show that effective leadership requires understanding.

Listening is hearing and valuing others (Wheeler, 2006); it involves actively acquiring employees' opinions, suggestions, and ideas. Employee commitment is increased when employees feel they have a voice within the organization's decision-making processes (Bass and Avolio, 1994). Bachler (1998) observes a positive relationship between Leadership and Listening. Servant leadership is characterized by listening as a characteristic that is crucial to leadership.

By operationalizing awareness, the leaders in an organization become capable of making any decision that will improve the organization and be aware of any signals in the environment (Barbuto, 2002). It is considered the key component of wisdom (Kant, 1978). Additionally, it plays an important role in the employee's emotional behavior (Caruso and Salvoey, 2002). An organization's effectiveness depends on its leaders being aware of its environment.

According to spears (1995), people who have failed or been disappointed in situations can resolve their emotional pain and broken spirits by healing. Healing is the most potent skill for effective Leadership (Ducher, 1999). A leader's primary responsibility is influencing employees' positive emotions to create a productive organization (Weymes, 2003). Leaders need to develop a team of employees and heal their emotions when a hard time occurs within an organization. Healing is similar to accepting, being humble, and forgiving (Fry, 2003). Therefore, healing is an appreciated quality of leadership.

Persuasion means convincing someone; leadership influences others without power (Barbuto and Wheeler, 2002). A leader's tactics include effective convincing qualities, where persuasion is more efficient than forceful influence, and its use in an ethical manner can benefit Leadership (Bass and Steidlmeier, 1999). Leadership efficiency can be enhanced by persuasion, according to this study.

Foresight is knowing what will be needed in the future that leaders and members use to anticipate future risks and consequences (Barbuto and Wheeler, 2002). According to Avolio (1999), leaders must understand an organization's future state to achieve success. Communication and anticipating the future are essential for leaders in an organization (Farling, 1999). Leadership requires foresight to anticipate current and future consequences.

For an organization, conceptualization involves forming a concept for something and fostering employee creativity (Spears, 1995; Barbuto, 2002). (Awamleh, 1999) The vision and content of an organization are related to its effectiveness. A stable mental model of a team is necessary for positive outcomes (Druskat, 2002). The conceptualizations play a key role in fostering an organizational environment.

Leaf (1996) states that servant leadership primarily aims at developing employees. Through development, leaders enhance employee satisfaction and loyalty, and employees and leaders have effective relationships (Sosik, 2000). Consequently, leaders who promote employee growth have a positive impact on organizations.

The concept of stewardship means taking care of the organization and enabling its members and organizations to contribute positively to society (Barbuto and Wheeler, 2002) because it addresses the needs of society. In addition to their organizational actions, good leaders show good behavior to the rest of society (Brief, 1986). In Servant Leadership, stewardship is one of the characteristics. Organizations adopt stewardship; they leave a positive legacy for their organization and contribute to society.

Community building is if the Organizational leaders are continually committed to their team and identify the issues that arise. Community work enables organizations to handle more appropriate problems. Leaders'

commitment to building a strong community is needed (Goffee, 2001). It shows that the leadership's community building makes the employees more passionate about the productive outcomes of the organizations.

2.3. Concept of Burnout

American researcher Freudenberg introduced burnout in the 1970s as a state of physical and mental exhaustion brought on by one's professional life. As a result of the literature review, it was found that burnout is caused by interpersonal and chronic emotional anxiety in the workplace (Maslach, Schaufeli, & Leiter, 2001). According to many researchers, increased organizational bullying leads to employee burnout and, ultimately, a quit (Faisal Khan, Sufyan, Naz, & Bibi, 2020; Laschinger, 2012). For more than 20 years, burnout has been studied at the organizational level and applied research has first examined industries with high interactivity. To define burnout, one needs to describe how employees feel physically and emotionally exhausted at work (Crawford, 2010). The term "burnout" refers to prolonged tension and stress, which can occur in any work occupation, anywhere in the world. Furthermore, Maslach and Jackson (1986) developed a measurement used for systematic research on burnout called Maslach burnout inventory (MBI). Burnout can be defined as emotional exhaustion (a form of mental and physical stress that is more chronic), depersonalization, or cynicism (developing a negative impression of others and a feeling of uncaring and hostility), and inefficacy (lack of achieving the goal in the workplace) that indicate poor performance (Maslach et al., 2001).

Khan et al. (2014) found that organizations with higher workloads experience higher levels of emotional exhaustion and disengagement (Mukundan & Khandehroo, 2010). Due to burnout and disengagement, the author developed the Oldenburg burnout inventory (OLBI), which consists of positive and negative items since burnout results in tired employees and a lack of engagement (Bakker, Demerouti, Boer, & Schaufeli, 2003). A person's self-efficacy and personality also play a role in work accomplishment criteria (Cordes & Dougherty, 1993).

Khan, Rasli, Khan, Yasir, and Malik (2014) consider burnout a burning issue. A work environment refers to emotional exhaustion and disengagement occurring continuously among employees (Maslach & Jackson., 1981). Experiencing emotional exhaustion results from extreme and prolonged stress due to particular working conditions (T. W. Lee & Mitchell, 1994). Freudenberg (1974) defined disengagement as distancing from a task. A psychological tension that reduces job performance, job satisfaction, low customer engagement, diminished organizational commitment, high absenteeism, and low self-esteem is result of this psychological tension (Lee & Ashforth, 1996; Shirom, 2005; Siegal & McDonald, 2004).

Relationship Between Transformational, Servant Leadership and Disengagement (Stone et al., 2004; Van Dierendonck, 2011) have investigated the association between transformational and servant leadership. These studies found a positive association between servant leadership and transformational leadership. By Liden (2008), Servant Leadership shows concern for community needs, while Transformational Leadership shows concern for organizational objectives. Similarly, the study elaborated on servant leadership, as it acts to 'serve' to attract social responsibilities. Accordingly, if someone doesn't want to grow, why force them?

Several studies show that servant leadership positively impacts employees' emotions, resulting in loyal and committed employees. A servant leadership approach focuses more on employees' emotional well-being and stability; as a result, employees' emotions are positive towards organizations and their leaders. Additionally, employees demonstrate greater emotional stability, low disengagement, and a lower emotional exhaustion level than others (David, Shoss, Johnson, and Witt, 2020).

The abilities of both types of leadership include motivation and visualization. According to Muthia and Krishnan (2015), transformational and servant leadership have many similarities. The servant and transformational leadership styles build strong bonds between leaders and their employees. As a result, employees are motivated, have high self-esteem, are more engaged at work, and are less likely to burnout. As part of transformational leadership, servants are encouraged to visualize their futures and be motivated toward tasks using persuasive tools. A transformational leadership vision is focused on the organization's benefits, whereas a servant leadership vision focuses on the employees' benefits (Faisal Khan, Bibi, Ahmed, & Naz, 2019). According to Jaramillo, Locander, and Mulki (2006), servant leadership increases employee engagement by reducing emotional fatigue. A study by Austin and Honeycutt (2011) found a positive correlation between Servant Leadership, productivity, and reduced burnout. Servant Leadership affects employee engagement positively.

According to Brewer and Clippard (2004), burnout affected 25% of job satisfaction, and emotional exhaustion and personal accomplishment negatively impacted it. Moreover, Khan, Khan, and Chaudhry (2015) conducted a study in Pakistan with 250 samples in a commercial organization to demonstrate that Servant Leadership positively impacts workplace spirituality and organizational culture moderate workplace spirituality (F Khan. et al., 2014).

One study conducted in 2020 by Desmarais, Harscher, and Zwingli on medical students, based on 167 students, of whom 58 percent were female, revealed that emotional exhaustion is reduced with a proper study demand and personal accomplishment is increased by the development of a new strategy for the appropriate syllabus of the students. A similar study will be conducted in Malaysia in 2020 on six selected public service sectors. There were 176 responses from civil servants regarding transformational leadership, public sector organizations, and public

service. Moreover, the study finds that civil servants' performance is positively related to the four dimensions of transformational leadership and negatively related to emotional exhaustion (F Khan, Sufyan, & Malik, 2020).

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

3. Research Methodology

In research methodology, the researcher uses a continuous process to conduct and answer their study. Methodology plays a significant role in determining the usefulness and precision of a research study, which are influenced by its method. The researcher chooses the best way to answer the research question using the research methodology. Also, it is a step-by-step process, following some rules and procedures. A type of investigation, it uncovers exciting and novel facts. It emphasized the importance of conducting research scientifically and using scientific methods and procedures to find answers to the questions. It is a scientific approach to dealing with a specific problem.

For a new research topic, the research design process is the entire process. This strategy involves steps incorporated with interrelated components that give the logical and desirable outcome about the topic of interest (Kumar, 2006)(F. Khan, Khan, & Malik, 2020). It involves collecting, analyzing, and interpreting data (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). A research design consists of a plan for collecting and analyzing the required information. In the social sciences, quantitative and qualitative approaches to research are used. In a qualitative approach, assumptions are based on judgment, observation, and statistical tools to confirm or disconfirm the hypotheses. In a quantitative approach, assumptions are based on numerical values and statistical tools.

Moreover, quantitative data are used to explain problems by getting numerical data and analyzing them using statistics. Furthermore, qualitative data related to human behavior and non-numerical data are also available (Faisal Khan. et al., 2014). Moreover, the researcher uses quantitative data analysis techniques in the current study, which generalize results from a large sample and use measurable statistics.

Moreover, longitudinal studies use repeated or continuous measurements to follow a selected sample over time; data are given from the selected sample to show changes over time (Yusoff, Khan, Mubeen, & Azam, 2013). Data were collected using a cross-sectional survey method in this study.

3.1. Population and Sampling

The set of all individuals or objects of interest is called Population (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). The population is the entire pool from which a sample can be selected. Population means the whole object; the researcher uses it to collect the data from 1183. In the current study, the researcher selected the Population of the three-health sector in the district of Swabi, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

Sampling plays a significant role in determining a population's statistical characteristics. Hanlon and Larger (2011) describe the sample as a subset of the population as a whole. It is more appropriate for a research study to have a sample size greater than 30 and less than 500 (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). Kumar (2005) indicates two types of sampling, probability sampling and non-probability sampling. Probability sampling refers to those types of sampling that allow for equal opportunity and independence in selecting participants. There is another sampling technique called non-probability sampling, where a predetermined and unequal chance of selection is considered. The convenience sampling technique was used in the current study to get many questionnaires quickly. From a population of 1183, 290 participants are selected (Krejcie & Morgan, 1970).

3.2. Research Instrument

Questionnaires are used in the current study, mainly open-ended and closed-ended questionnaires. Researchers provide closed-ended questions with options from which participants can choose. On the other hand, open-ended questions give choices for participants to answer on their way. As part of this study, the researcher used a closed-ended questionnaire. Additionally, it is a faster and more natural way to answer the research question. Five-Likert scales were used for all instruments (strongly disagree to strongly agree). Each item in the research instrument contains four sections; the first is about defining demographic variables (gender, age, occupation, job timing, experience, nature of the job). Adapted from (Rafferty & Griffin, 2004), the second section contains 15 leadership question items with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.89. It contains Servant Leadership 23 scales adapted from (Searle & Barbuto Jr, 2011) with 0.879 reliability. OLB adapted from (Demerouti., Mostert, & Bakker, 2010; Khan., Rasli, & Zahra, 2020) will be used to measure disengagement items 09 and their reliability in the fourth part. (Faisal Khan et al., 2016).

4. Final data analysis

Data analysis is a process that inspects, cleans, transforms and models data. Data was collected through five Likert scales from the primary source, fed into MS Excel, imported into SPSS (statistical package for social sciences) Version 21 to run the different tests. Descriptive statistics will be used for demographic questions; the researcher will use the hierarchical regression method to investigate hypotheses.

4.1. Response Rate and Properties of Respondents

During the current study, data were collected from various hospitals in the district of Swabi Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. There were 987 employees in district Swabi, and 290 were sampled (Krejcie & Morgan, 1970). Was distributed 300 questionnaires, 254 of which were received, 25 were incomplete, and 229 were analyzed for the final results. The response rate was 90%. In the adapted questionnaire, demographic information includes gender, age, experience, and nature of the job. In district Swabi Pakistan, 135 male employees, 58.9% of the whole sample, worked in the health sector, while 94 female employees, 41.1%. It is important to note that this study has different categories of respondents by age. In Figure 2, the highest age is 40, which is 67 in number with a percentage of 29.2, between the ages of 36 and 40, with a frequency of 41 with 17.9%, between the ages of 31 and 35, with a frequency of 85 with 37.1%, between the ages of 26 and 30, with 26 representing 11.3%. In contrast, only one represents the age below 25 with 0.4%. A breakdown of employee experience is provided in Figure 2, where 10 employees have less than one year's experience, 1 to 3 employees have a 19.6% percentage, 83 employees with 3 to 5 years of experience were counted in the distribution Figure with 36.2%, followed by 18.7% for employees with 5 to 10 years with 43, and 20.9% for employees with over 10 years.

Figure 2: Properties of Respondents

4.2. Descriptive statistics

Descriptive statistics provide data summaries in mean, median, and mode (Ali and Bhaskar, 2015). The data set is summarized, simplified, appraised, and controlled in a descriptive study using descriptive statistics. It is used for averages, like Mean, Median, variance and standard deviation (Kamal, 2013). A mean is equal to the average of all scores; a median is equal to the middle value; and a variance equals the sum of all squared deviations divided by the number of participants (Zeller and Richard, 1999; Jankowski and Flannelly, 2015). The purpose of descriptive statistics is to summarize the complete data set, calculate the mean and standard deviation, and draw conclusions from the mean. The standard deviation was obtained using the square root of the variance (Nile, 2016). A standard deviation shows the dispersion data from the mean. Table 1 describes the sample data collected and their measures, with servant leadership as an independent variable, disengagement as a dependent variable, and transformational leadership as a moderating variable.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Alpha coefficient
Servant leadership	265	3.8515	.41457	0.87
Disengagement	265	2.8399	.85981	0.77
Transformational leadership	265	3.8088	.49014	0.93

4.3. Reliability

The objective is to determine whether a particular result is reliable and consistent by determining whether or not the result is consistent and reliable. For example, the written test is similar to the practical experience during the training process. (Vincent & Wu, 2000) Compares the reliability of items using the Cronbach coefficient alpha as a criterion. The most important statistics in reliability research have been considered by Cronbach alpha and are all within acceptable limits.

4.4. Normality

Kurtosis and skewness are used to check the normality of a frequency distribution; kurtosis measures a sample's peak or flatness on a standard curve. It is called mesokurtic when the Peaked curve is positively distributed, leptokurtic when it is flat, and platykurtic when it is negative (Corder and Foreman, 2011). Field (2013) also found the kurtosis value between +2 and -2. Furthermore, skewness measures sample symmetry on the assumed normal distribution if a long tail is found at the left edge of the curve, known as negative skewness. Positively skewed curves have a long tail on the right side. In the case of a P-value greater than 0.05, it does not suggest normality, and in the opposite case, it does. The current study will use a normality test to determine whether the data is normally distributed.

Normality was checked for skewness and kurtosis of the data. Servant leadership has skewness and kurtosis values of 11.4 and 12.7, while -2.59. Disengagement and transformational leadership have skewness and kurtosis values of 1.52 and -2.38, respectively. The graphic representations of normality are presented in Figures 3 and 4.

Table 2 Skewness and kurtosis

Variables	N	SKEWNESS		KURTOSIS	
		Statistic	Std. error	Statistic	Std. error
Servant Leadership	265	1.724	.150	3.790	.298
Disengagement	265	-.229	.150	-.710	.298
Transformational Leadership	265	1.466	.150	2.462	.298

Figure 3: Normality between Servant Leadership and Disengagement

Table 3: Regression Analysis of Servant Leadership and Disengagement

Servant Leadership	Disengagement	
	Unstandardized Coefficients B	t
	- 0.380	-0.3023
R Square	0.034	
Adjust R square	0.030	
F-Model	10.137**	

** p<0.01

4.5. Testing Hypotheses

H1: There is an effect of servant Leadership on Disengagement

Disengagement and servant leadership have a negative relationship, as shown in Table 3.

Disengagement was also tested as a result of servant leadership. Table 3 indicates the R square value is (0.034), meaning 34% of changes occur in the dependent variable due to the independent variable. It shows that servant leadership affects (0.030) disengagement, the dependent variable. According to Table 4.8, an increase in servant leadership will decrease the dependent variable Disengagement by a value of (-.380).

H2: Transformational leadership moderates the relationship between servant leadership and disengagement

For testing, the moderation effect of TL among the SL and Dis. The independent variable in the current study is servant leadership; the moderator variable is transformational leadership; the dependent variable is disengagement. In the first model, the SL is associated with the dependent variable, Disengagement. Using Model 01, Table 4 shows that servant leadership affects disengagement by 34%, with a 30% change (Model 1). In the second model, the TL is entered with the dependent variable Disengagement. According to (Model 02), SL and TL changes influence disengagement by 52%, whereas disengagement variance is 45%. In the Third model, the SL, TL and interaction between SL and TL are entered with the dependent variable Disengagement. Additionally, in model 03, the 55% change occurred with a variation of (0.044) due to the interaction of (SL / TL).

Table 4 Hierarchical Regression Analysis of TL between SL and DIS

Model 01	Disengagement	
	Unstandardized Coefficients B	t value
Servant Leadership	-0.380	-3.023
Adjusted R Square	0.030	
R Square	0.034	
F-Model	11.137**	
Model 02		
Servant Leadership	-0.401	-0.210
Transformational Leadership	-0.374	-0.268
Adjusted R Square	0.045	
R Square	0.052	
F-Model	12.213**	
Model 03		
Servant Leadership	-0.074	-0.361
Transformational Leadership	-0.390	-0.231
Interaction (SL × TL)	-0.417	-1.341
Adjusted R Square	0.044	
R Square	0.055	
F-Model	11.214**	

** p<0.01

5. Conclusion and Discussion

This study aims to enrich our understanding of the effect of servant leadership on employee disengagement in the health sector. The model also explains how Transformational Leadership plays a moderating role between servant leadership, emotional exhaustion, and disengagement. Using conceptual models and theories such as the job-fit theory developed by Kalleberg (1995, 1998), the transformational leadership theory developed, and the social identity theory developed by Tajfel (1979). Divya and Suganthi (2018) found that servant leadership improved employee disengagement, which is consistent with studies by Hakanen and Schaufeli (2012). The current study also examines the moderator role of transformational leadership, similar to that in the study (Malik and Farooqi, 2013). As a result of combining transformational leadership with servant leadership, the present study found that employee burnout is buffered and results are improved.

First, the study examines the independent variable effects of servant leadership on disengagement among health sector employees in district Swabi. The health sector is more conducive to servant leadership (Farrington & Lillah, 2018). Servant leadership in the health sector has the serving nature that professionals need (Schwartz et al., 2002). In the present study, servant leadership reduced employee disengagement in the health sector. It means this type of leadership has a positive effect on employees. Employee burnout can be reduced when servant leadership is applied within the hospital industry. A satisfied and responsible employee is more likely to use resources carefully, less likely to feel overwhelmed by job demands, and better relate to patients. Due to applied supportive management, nurses are always presentable for patients (Bartram, Casimir, Djurkovic, Leggat, & Stanton, 2012). When servant leadership is applied within management, it positively affects other staff.

The current study result also provides additional information that there was a strong negative relationship between servant leadership and emotional exhaustion, aligned with a previous study (Tang, Kwan Zhang and Zhu, 2015). It also shows a negative association between servant leadership and disengagement. Not cynical employees feel more committed to their jobs (Brown, Slater, & Lofters, 2019). As a result of the current study, it has been concluded that servant leadership decreases disengagement among employees, thereby confirming our main conclusion, which was based on the first objective of the study, that servant leadership has a positive impact on disengagement, and this is consistent with previous research findings (Divya & Suganthi, 2018).

The study investigates the moderating effect of transformational leadership on the association between servant leadership and disengagement. Transformational leadership is negatively correlated with disengagement, say the researchers. Furthermore, researchers find a negative relationship between servant leadership and disengagement. Transformational leadership and servant leadership have a positive relationship. Some researchers say transformational leadership can positively affect emotions. Consequently, it provides more motivation for learning and growth of the employees, resulting in low employee burnout. A transformational leader positively impacts employee engagement (Hina, Farhan, & Hussain, 2019).

The current study found that transformational leadership is linked to the emotional feelings of employees, in line with previous research. Therefore, in the present research, transformational leadership is used as a moderator variable between servant leadership and disengagement. According to the researcher, servant and transformational leadership have a positive relationship. Additionally, transformational leadership increases the other types of leadership and creates an environment of immense confidence among staff (Zhu et al., 2012).

As researchers know, both transformational and servant leadership styles are positive styles of leadership, which is the focus of the current study. Previously, the researcher found that servant leadership has a positive emotional impact on employees in the health sector (Farrington, 2018). Similarly, Servant leadership positively affects engagement. Low stress makes employees more engaged in their work. In addition, transformational leadership creates an environment that cultivates creativity, motivation, and commitment.

Servant leadership is more effective when it uses transformational leadership in the health sector (Jafai et al., 2016), and decreases burnout among employees. Ultimately, servant leadership was effective when combined with transformational leadership. It creates more engaged employees is in line with the study (Divya & Suganthi, 2018).

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

There are several aspects of disengagement that can be addressed by the current study, which is helpful in the hospital sector. The article also provides insight into two leadership styles that could reduce job burnout, especially in the health sector. The unique knowledge of capable organizations gains precise advantages in the industry. Researchers will benefit from the findings of this study. The study makes a strong contribution to leadership research, which enriches the body of literature. In addition, this study will help employees identify under which conditions they suffer from burnout and how they might improve their work and avoid its negative effects.

Furthermore, a competent manager is a company's most valuable asset. Two distinct types of leadership are discussed in this study, together with a few practical implications. In organizations, managers use these leadership styles for training and development sessions. The subordinates avoid many of the negative results. The manager can also identify the employee's strain and stress and create balancing situations that contribute to the organization's success. As a manager the study shows that if the manager utilizes both leadership styles effectively, employees are protected from burnout and stress-free environments are created.

As a result, policymakers can make informed decisions about different sectors based on the evidence provided in this study. Therefore, when evidence of the current result is available, they will adopt a flexible policy in the health sector and other sectors. Moreover, the accessibility of the present study is important for policymakers to collect the information they need quickly and efficiently.

Researchers have made significant contributions to practical and managerial aspects of research. The study, however, has some limitations that should be considered. There are three dimensions of burnout, but only two have been considered in this study. The scope of this research is unable to understand the third dimension of burnout. A second limitation is that this study has a limited cultural context, making it impossible to generalize and has a limited sample size. Third, due to limitations of time and resources, the researcher used a cross-sectional data collection study. Finally, the study limitation was using a self-report questionnaire as the survey method.

The focus of the present research is to identify the main effect of servant leadership on two burnout dimensions' disengagement in the health sector and the indirect role of transformational leadership in reducing the negative effects of employee burnout dimensions. It also recognizes the importance of servant and transformational leadership. In light of these findings, future recommendations will be made. Other researchers should conduct studies on burnout using qualitative and quantitative approaches and include the third dimension: reduced performance or incompetence. Further, future researchers should conduct longitudinal studies to achieve good

results. During the time interval, the variables of the current study may change. This study is focused on the health sector, while other studies have looked at burnout dimensions and leadership types in industry and education.

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